

593 **Table S1.** Traits quantified to determine myrmecomorphy, after Kelly et al. (2021).

Characteristic	Quantification formula	Note
1: Thin legs	1 – width leg III femur / length leg III femur	-
2: Elongation of cephalothorax	1 – cephalothorax width / cephalothorax length	-
3: Elongation of abdomen	1 – abdomen width / abdomen length	-
4: Elongation of pedicel	pedicel length / total body length	-
5: Constriction of the cephalothorax	1 – cephalothorax width at point of constriction / cephalothorax width at widest point	in dorsal view
6: Constriction of the cephalothorax	1 – cephalothorax height at point of constriction / cephalothorax height at highest point	in lateral view
7: Constriction of the abdomen	1 – abdomen width at point of constriction / abdomen width at widest point	in dorsal view
8: Constriction of the abdomen	1 – abdomen height at point of constriction / abdomen height at highest point	in lateral view
9: Illusion by coloration	i) transverse band or stripe of lightly colored setae on the cephalothorax creating the illusion of a separation into a head and thorax	scored based on the presence of the illusion by coloration traits i-iii (i.e., single trait = 0.334, two traits = 0.667, and all three traits = 1.0)

	ii) transverse band or stripe of lightly colored setae on the abdomen creating the illusion of a separation into a petiole (or postpetiole) and abdomen
	iii) darkening of the area surrounding the posterior lateral eye creating the illusion of only two large compound eyes
Overall mimic accuracy	(A + B + C + D + E + F + G + H + I) / 9

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596 **Table S2.** Corrected Akaike information criterion weight (AICcw) values based on the consensus tree
 597 for the Castianeirinae and Myrmarachnini indicating the relative likelihood fit of the mimic accuracy
 598 data and the nine selected myrmecomorphic traits using Brownian motion (BM), Ornstein-Uhlenbeck
 599 (OU) and Early Burst (EB) models of evolution. The favored model (highest value) is in bold.

Characteristic	MODEL TYPE		
	BM	OU	EB
Castianeirinae			
Thin legs	0.000	1.000	0.000
Elongation of cephalothorax	0.000	1.000	0.000
Elongation of abdomen	0.000	1.000	0.000
Elongation of pedicel	0.000	1.000	0.000
Lateral constriction of cephalothorax	0.046	0.016	0.938
Dorsal constriction of cephalothorax	0.000	0.000	1.000
Lateral constriction of abdomen	0.000	1.000	0.000
Dorsal constriction of abdomen	0.182	0.755	0.063
Myrmarachnini			
Thin legs	0.000	1.000	0.000
Elongation of cephalothorax	0.004	0.994	0.002
Elongation of abdomen	0.000	1.000	0.000
Elongation of pedicel	0.000	1.000	0.000
Lateral constriction of cephalothorax	0.001	0.999	0.000
Dorsal constriction of cephalothorax	0.001	0.999	0.000
Lateral constriction of abdomen	0.000	1.000	0.000
Dorsal constriction of abdomen	0.000	1.000	0.000

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